

SYNTHESIS IN THE 3-AZAFLUORENE GROUP. PART II. A NEW SYNTHESIS OF 3-AZAFLUORENONE

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7 : 8-Benzoisoquinoline has been unambiguously synthesised and degraded to 3-azafluorenone.

In Part I of this series compounds of the 3-azafluorene group have been reached from difficult accessible pyridine derivatives (Chatterjea and Prasad, *Chem. Ber.*, 1960, **93**, in press). It transpired that compounds of this group should be accessible by degradation of a suitable polynuclear heterocyclic compound (cf. Skraup and Gobenzl, *Monatsh.*, 1883, **4**, 436 ; *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2306 ; Ciusa and Buono, *Gazzetta*, 1950, **80**, 864 ; Koelsch and Steinhauer, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 1516) and for this purpose, 7 : 8-benzoisoquinoline (I) or its derivatives appeared as attractive intermediates. In fact, (I) was readily oxidised with boiling potassium permanganate to afford 3-*o*-carboxyphenyl-isonicotinic acid (II) which on pyrolysis furnished 3-azafluorenone (III), identical with the specimen obtained before.

As the synthesis of 7 : 8-benzoisoquinoline by Koelsch and Lindquist (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 657) was both laborious and ambiguous, an alternative synthesis was undertaken. 2-Naphthaldehyde, now prepared conveniently by the reduction of 2-naphthonitrile by lithium triethoxyaluminumhydride (Brown *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, III, 9) was converted into the related acrylic acid by condensation with malonic acid and then reduced and cyclised to the known 6:7-benzoin-dan-1-one (Cook and Hewett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1098). The 2-isonitroso derivative (V) on the Beckmann rearrangement with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in alkali, followed by hydrolysis, yielded 1-carboxynaphthalene-2-acetic acid (VI). This was followed by esterification with diazomethane, condensation with methyl formate and cyclisation of the resulting hydroxymethylene compound with warm hydrochloric acid to methyl 7 : 8-benzoisocoumarin-4-carboxylate (VII). This was hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid and decarboxylated to 7 : 8-benzoisocoumarin (VIII). This on heating with ethanolic ammonia afforded 1-hydroxy-7 : 8-benzoisoquinoline (IX), also described by Koelsch and Lindquist (*loc. cit.*) by an entirely different method. 7 : 8-Benzoisoquinoline was obtained from it by reduction of the 1-chloro derivative with palladised charcoal and hydrogen in presence of sodium hydroxide in ethanolic solution (cf. Bailey *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2277).

(VII : R = CO₂Me)

(VIII : R = H)

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII : R = OH)

(XIV : R = Br)

The recent elegant work of Reihe and Schmitz (*Chem. Ber.*, 1956, 89, 1254; cf. Schmitz, *ibid.*, 1958, 91, 1133) on the new synthesis of isoquinolines prompted us to attempt the synthesis of (I) along the same lines. 2-β-Naphthylethanol, now prepared in excellent yield by reduction of ethyl β-naphthylacetate by lithium aluminium hydride, furnished 7:8-benzoisochroman (X) in moderate yield on treatment with paraformaldehyde along with di-(β-2-hydroxyethyl-α-naphthyl)methane (XI), characterised as its 3:5-dinitrobenzoate. Bromination of (X) to the 1-bromo derivative (XIII) was not smooth and led to complex mixtures; attempts to isolate the rearranged aldehyde (XIV) from the crude product by way of the bisulphite compound was unsuccessful. However, treatment of the crude brominated product with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine furnished a small quantity of the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (XIII).

During this work, 1-methyl-7:8-benzoisoquinoline (XVI) was also prepared by Pictet-Gam's cyclisation of *N*-acetyl-2-hydroxy-2-(β-naphthyl)ethylamine (XV), now readily obtained by the reduction of ω-acetamido-β-acetonaphthone (Day and Immediata, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 512) by potassium borohydride. The yield of the isoquinoline (XVI) was so poor that further work was not possible.

* EXPERIMENTAL

2-Naphthaldehyde.—2-Naphthonitrile (1 M) was added to a solution of lithium triethoxyaluminumhydride (prepared by careful addition of 1.5N ethyl acetate to 1.3M lithium aluminium hydride in dry ethereal solution), maintained at -2° . After the addition the mixture was stirred for 3 hours at 0° and the excess of the hydride destroyed by the addition of methanol. The mixture was worked up in the usual manner to afford 2-naphthaldehyde, yield 50% (crude).

6:7-Benzoindan-1-one.—A mixture of the crude 2-naphthaldehyde (10 g.), malonic acid (30 g.), piperidine (2 c.c.) and pyridine (50 c.c.) was heated on a water-bath for 6 hours when the reaction was practically over. On working up, β -2-naphthylacrylic acid was obtained, m.p. 195° (Rousset, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1897, 17, 813, records m.p. 196°), yield 12.2 g.

The acrylic acid (10 g.) was suspended in water and sodium amalgam (400 g., 2.5%) was added in small lots to the warm mixture ($40-50^{\circ}$) with stirring. The reaction was considered complete when no more of the acrylic acid separated as the sodium salt on cooling. β -2-Naphthylpropionic acid was obtained on acidification, crystallising from aqueous ethanol in colorless plates, m.p. 135° (Mayer and Sieglitz, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 1855, record m.p. 135°), yield 8.9 g.

The propionic acid was cyclised according to Cook and Hewett (*loc. cit.*) by warming with stannic chloride. After decomposition with water, the indanone was extracted from the resulting solid by ether (yield 8 g.). A considerable portion of the compound remained as insoluble *tin complex* from which the ketone was recovered (about 3 g.) by extracting with boiling pyridine. Attempted cyclisation of the propionic acid with trifluoroacetic anhydride gave only a tar even at the room temperature.

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange-red needles, m.p. 295° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.30. $C_{19}H_{13}O_4N_4$ requires N, 15.46%.)

2-isoNitroso-6:7-benzoindan-1-one.—The above indanone (8 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (25 c.c.) containing amyl nitrite (15 g.) and warmed on the water-bath. To the stirred solution HCl (conc., 6 c.c.) was added and the stirring continued for 1 hour. The *isonitroso* derivative, which separated gradually on cooling, was collected and crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. $234-35^{\circ}$ (decomp.), yield 7.5 g. (Found: N, 6.80. $C_{13}H_9O_2N$ requires N, 6.63%.)

1-Carboxynaphthalene-2-acetic Acid.—A solution of the *isonitroso* compound (6 g.) in warm 10% NaOH solution (60 c.c.) was gradually treated with stirring with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (8 g.) at 40° and the solution completed by heating the mixture on the water-bath. 10% NaOH solution (40 c.c.) was further added, the mixture refluxed for 4 hours, cooled, acidified and extracted with ether when the *acetic acid* was obtained as sandy prisms, yield 5 g. For analysis, the compound was crystallised from water (charcoal) and obtained in colorless prisms, m.p. $184-85^{\circ}$ (gas evolution). (Found: C, 67.23; H, 4.60. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.83; H, 4.38%.)

* All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

The crude acid (4.9 g.) was esterified by treatment with an excess of ethereal diazomethane. The *dimethyl ester* distilled at 184°/2 mm and obtained as a thick viscous liquid, yield 4.12 g. (Found: C, 70.01; H, 5.60. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 69.75; H, 5.46%).

7:8-Benzoisocoumarin.—A mixture of the foregoing ester (4 g.) in dry ether (40 c.c.) and methyl formate (5 g.) was added to anhydrous sodium methoxide (from sodium, 0.8 g.), stirred at the room temperature and left overnight. Next day, more methyl formate (3 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 1 hour. After removal of the ether, the residue was dissolved in water (12 c.c.) and warmed on the water-bath after addition of acetic acid (5 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 5 c.c.). *Methyl 7:8-benzoisocoumarin-4-carboxylate* separated in fine silky needles, yield 2.9 g. The compound was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 157°. (Found: C, 70.63; H, 4.18. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.85; H, 3.96%).

The ester (2.8 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (6 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 8 c.c.) for 12 hours. This was cooled, diluted with water and the crystalline mass so obtained consisted of a mixture of *7:8-benzoisocoumarin* (1.5 g.) and *7:8-benzoisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid* (1.2 g.), separated with the help of sodium bicarbonate. The latter (m.p. of the crude material, 249°) was mixed with copper-bronze (0.1 g.) and decarboxylated by heating above the melting point, and then on distillation in vacuum, *7:8-benzoisocoumarin* was obtained; total yield 2.1 g. The *isocoumarin* was crystallised from ethanol as a colorless crystalline mass, m.p. 144°. (Found: C, 79.50; H, 4.43. $C_{18}H_8O_2$ requires C, 79.56; H, 4.11%).

1-Hydroxy-7:8-benzoisoquinoline.—A mixture of the foregoing *isocoumarin* (2.0 g.) and ethanolic ammonia (10 c.c., saturated at 0°) was heated at 140° in a sealed tube for 10 hours. *1-Hydroxy-7:8-benzoisoquinoline* separated from the alcoholic solution in nearly colorless prismatic needles. It was purified by sublimation in vacuum, m.p. 202° (Koelsch and Lindquist, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 200-201°). (Found: N, 7.23. Calc. for $C_{13}H_9ON$: N, 7.18%).

7:8-Benzoisoquinoline.—The above hydroxyisoquinoline was converted into *1-chloro-7:8-benzoisoquinoline* according to Koelsch and Lindquist (*loc. cit.*). This chloro compound (1.2 g.) was dissolved in methanol containing KOH (0.5 g.) and shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in the presence of palladised charcoal (0.4 g., 5%). Hydrogenation was complete in 20 minutes. The mixture was filtered and the alcoholic filtrate worked up to furnish *7:8-benzoisoquinoline* in 0.95 g. yield. The *picrate* was crystallised from butanol in yellow needles, m.p. 232° (Koelsch and Lindquist, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 216°). (Found: C, 56.00; H, 3.10. Calc. for $C_{13}H_9N$: $C_6H_3O_7N_3$, C, 55.88; H, 2.97%). The *picrolonate* crystallised from butanol in a yellow crystalline mass, m.p. 278-80° (decomp.). (Found: N, 16.09. $C_{13}H_9N.C_{10}H_6O_5N_4$ requires N, 15.79%).

3-o-Carboxyphenylisonicotinic Acid.—A mixture of *7:8-benzoisoquinoline* (0.85 g.) and water (80 c.c.) was boiled under reflux while a saturated solution of $KMnO_4$ (2.2 g.) in water was added during 30 minutes. Oxidation was rapid and complete. The mixture was filtered, residual manganese dioxide washed with water and the filtrate concentrated to a small bulk (5 c.c.) and acidified with acetic acid, when the dibasic acid separated as colorless leaflets, m.p. 265° (decomp), yield 0.5 g. *UV spectrum*: End on absorption in ethanol. (Found: N, 5.34. $C_{13}H_9O_4N$ requires: N, 5.76%).

3-Azafluorenone.—The above dicarboxylic acid (0.45 g.) was pyrolysed at about 360° (metal bath) for 10 minutes in a test tube. The whole was extracted with hot benzene and filtered through an alumina column; the yellow band which was eluted with benzene was collected. *3-Azafluorenone* was extracted from the benzene solution by HCl (dilute), the acid extract made alkaline and

extracted with ether. On removal of the ether, 3-azafluorenone was obtained as lemon-yellow crystals, crystallising from a small volume of ethanol in yellow plates, m.p. 128-29°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained earlier (Part I, *loc. cit.*), yield 15 mg.

β-2-Naphthylethanol.—A solution of ethyl 2-naphthylacetate (30 g.) in ether (50 c.c.) was cautiously added to a slurry of LiAlH_4 (10 g.) in ether (100 c.c.). The addition was maintained at such a rate so as to keep the ether boiling. After the addition the mixture was refluxed for ½ hour and the excess of the hydride destroyed by the addition of ethyl acetate and finally with HCl (dilute). The ethereal solution was separated, dried with anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the residue after removal of the ether was distilled in vacuum. *β*-2-Naphthylethanol was obtained as a colorless solid, m.p. 70-71° (Sontag, *Compt. rend.*, 1933, **197**, 1130, records m.p. 65-68°), yield 23 g.

7:8-Benzoisochroman.—A mixture of *β*-2-naphthylethanol (22 g.), paraformaldehyde (5.5 g.) in dry carbon disulphide (125 c.c.), cooled in a freezing mixture, was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride with mechanical stirring. There was an immediate separation of a crystalline solid which gradually went into solution. The passage of hydrogen chloride was continued for 8 hours and the mixture left overnight at the room temperature. Next day, the mixture was treated with ice-cold water, organic layer removed, dried and the solvent distilled. The residual liquid was heated at 100° in vacuum (30 mm) for 3 hours and then distilled under reduced pressure. 7:8-Benzoisochroman was obtained as a colorless mobile liquid, b.p. 150-55°/2.5 mm, solidifying to a colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 38-40° (from petroleum ether), yield 12.5 g. (Found: C, 84.50; H, 6.79. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.74; H, 6.58%).

The picrate was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 134-35°. (Found: N, 10.12. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires N, 10.17%).

The higher boiling residue distilled at 270-75°/2.5 mm, solidified on keeping and was obtained as colorless plates, m.p. 58°, and was identified as di-(*β*-2-hydroxyethyl-*α*-naphthyl)methane (XI), yield 5.1 g. (Found: C, 83.89; H, 6.95. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 84.23; H, 6.79%).

The di-3:5-dinitrobenzoate, prepared in pyridine, was crystallised from ethanol in nearly colorless crystalline powder, m.p. 174°. (Found: N, 7.91. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires N, 7.52%).

Bromination of 7:8-benzoisochroman.—To a solution of the isochroman (10 g.) in dry CCl_4 (10 c.c.) a solution of bromine (8 g.) in the same solvent (10 c.c.) was added in bright sunlight. The addition of bromine produced a turbidity (due to the separation of an intermediate oily compound) which gradually disappeared. When all the bromine had been added, the mixture was irradiated with ultraviolet light and then refluxed on the water-bath for ½ hour. By this time, the deep brown colour of the mixture disappeared, forming a straw-yellow solution. After the removal of the solvent, the residue was heated at 140° under vacuum for one hour and then distilled. The fraction, b.p. 180-90°/2.5 mm, did not afford any bisulphite compound on stirring for several days with a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite. Nevertheless, on prolonged boiling with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in ethanol containing phosphoric acid, the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (XIII) was obtained, crystallising from a large volume of acetic acid as orange-red plates, m.p. 274°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 59.35; H, 4.00. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires C, 59.99; H, 4.24%).

N-Acetyl-*β*-hydroxy-*β*-(2-naphthyl)ethylamine.—*ω*-Acetamido-2-acetonaphthone (2.5 g.) (Day and Immediata, *loc. cit.*) was suspended in water (50 c.c.) and stirred vigorously. To this an aqueous solution of potassium borohydride (2.0 g. in 10 c.c. of water) was added gradually. Stirring

was continued for 10 hours and the frothing kept under control by the addition of a few drops of ether. After setting the mixture aside overnight, the fine silky needles were collected, washed with ice-cold water, and obtained as silky needles on crystallisation from water, m.p. 95°. (Dey and Rajagopalan, *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 5086, record m.p. 96°), yield, 1.2 g.

7:8-Benzo-1-methylisoquinoline.—The above acetyl compound (0.5 g.) was dissolved in xylene (30 c.c.), treated with phosphoric anhydride (3 g.), boiled and stirred mechanically. Further amounts of phosphoric anhydride (2×3.0 g.) were added at the interval of ½ hour. After heating for 1½ hours, the mixture was cooled and worked up to afford the *isoquinoline* as an oil in a very small quantity. This readily furnished a *picrate*, m.p. 245°, from ethanol. (Found: C, 57.00; H, 3.20; N, 12.95. $C_{14}H_{11}N.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires C, 56.87; H, 3.34; N, 13.27%).

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